

MONETARY SYSTEM OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN AND ITS ELEMENTS

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Abstract: This article describes the monetary reforms in our country in detail. Monetary policy is very important for every country. Therefore, we can say that the reform of this system will ensure the financial attractiveness of that country.

Key words: monetary reform, financial stability, economic independence, banking and credit sector, future of countries, etc.

The situation that was formed in the late 1980s under the influence of the economic mechanism, which was left unchanged for many years, became obsolete and ineffective, and the ineffectiveness of the economic reforms implemented by the former Union government made the situation even more complicated. In particular, the mechanism of reconstruction of the national economy, which began in 1986, does not have a solid foundation, its content was not clearly understood from the beginning, but it was officially aimed at increasing the pace of socio-economic development of the country.

As a result, the main macroeconomic indicators of the former Union decreased, and at the beginning of 1989, the disproportion (deficit) of the state budget's income and expenses was 140 billion. amounted to rubles and the amount of money emission was much higher than the acceptable level, the savings of the population in the form of money were more than 5 times compared to the stock of goods. As a result, in 1989-1991, the prices of many products began to rise,

inflationary processes increased, production volumes in industry and agriculture decreased. As imbalances deepened, the level of supply and demand for the ability to pay decreased, the growth of the population's real income stopped, and stagnation began to manifest itself more clearly. It was not possible to end the growth of macroeconomic instability caused by a number of external and internal factors. If in 1985-1988 the average GDP growth of Uzbekistan was 5.2 percent, then in 1989-1991 this figure was 1.6 percent on average. Since 1992, under the influence of various factors, a decrease in GDP began to be observed.

In particular, in 1992, the largest indicator of the decline of Uzbekistan's GDP (11.1 percent) was recorded. However, as a result of the wise and effective economic policy of the country's leadership, in the next three years, that is, in 1993-1995, the tendency of the GDP to decrease sharply in the republic was curbed. For example, during this period, GDP decreased by 39% in Russia, 40% in Ukraine, 43% in Kazakhstan, and 48% in Kyrgyzstan, while this decrease was only 7.8% in the republic. During the implementation of historically important economic reforms in the first years of independence, certain conflicts, contradictions and imbalances arose. In particular, the price imbalance was manifested in the decrease in the prices of raw materials and agricultural products and in the increase in the prices of final products and consumer goods. One of the reasons for this disparity was the preservation of the procedure for setting prices for certain goods for the purpose of social protection of the population. Because maintaining limited prices for some goods required a large amount of budget funds.

The decision-making of the President of our country with restraint and careful study of the situation in solving problems that require a certain amount of time, structural reforms, and large funds has yielded positive results. The gradual and consistent implementation of economic reforms allowed Uzbekistan to avoid a sharp deterioration of economic conditions compared to other CIS countries. In

the first years of independence, before the introduction of the national currency "Soum" into circulation, the growth of hidden macroeconomic instability, which accumulated during the years of the planned economy, unfortunately continued objectively. At the same time, in accordance with the principles of transition set by the President of Uzbekistan, along with the careful and gradual cancellation of state orders and subsidies, unlike other countries, the centralized regulation and control in many industries and sectors is the key to the success of the reforms. was an important factor. Such an acceptable economic policy helped prevent economic collapse in the early years of independence in our young country.

The complexity of this stage was that two important tasks had to be solved at once. The first of these was to overcome the severe consequences of the administrative-command system, to end the tension, to stabilize the economy, and the second was to form the foundations of market relations, taking into account the specific conditions and characteristics of the republic. In the conditions of economic reforms and macroeconomic instability, from the first year of independence, the President paid special attention to the social protection of the population and took this factor into account when determining every measure of the reforms. As part of the measures to consistently continue price reforms, starting from January 10, 1992, the republic switched to contractual (free) prices and tariffs for production-technical goods, consumer goods, works and services. In order to protect the population, the government of the Republic has set the prices of some industrial goods and the limited amounts of tariffs for some types of services provided to the population.

A part of the costs of importing grain to producers, production of bread, flour and other food products, as well as the costs incurred in connection with the provision of free breakfasts and preferential meals by public catering enterprises to schoolchildren and students, will be covered from the republican budget. In 1992, This helped keep retail prices steady throughout 1992. In 1993, a sharp increase in

prices, a rapid increase in the amount of money in circulation and the volume of credit funds, and the provision of large-scale subsidies to enterprises accelerated the collapse of the single ruble zone. Along with the process of establishing its own financial system in the republic, there was also an increase in the state budget deficit caused by the suspension of allocations from the Union budget, as well as an increase in expenditures on subsidies and allocations from the budget. Despite the fact that funds from the Union budget have stopped and the volume of production has actually decreased, the stability of the financial situation has been ensured, the limitation of state expenditures has been achieved, and the deficit in the state budget has not been allowed to grow in the republic. For this purpose, tax-budget and monetary policies have been tightened. Funds were allocated from the budget month by month and it was implemented only within the received funds. As a result of the implemented consistent and drastic measures, it was possible to reduce the state budget deficit to less than 4% of the gross domestic product in these years, in particular, to reduce its growth by 1.7 times during 1994. The elements of the monetary system are interconnected and thus ensure the integrity of the system. However, some elements of the monetary system continue to develop and have a direct and strong impact on the system itself, on the state of the economy, at certain periodic intervals. For example, a sharp increase in the money supply leads to an increase in the inflation rate and, therefore, to a decrease in the value of money. OR an increase in the real exchange rate of the national currency can lead to a decrease in the country's export potential and thus to a decrease in the supply of foreign currencies. This creates a negative impact on the stability of the national currency.

It is worth noting that the introduction of the price scale, which is an element of the money system, made it possible to introduce a regime of strictly defined exchange rates on a global scale. It was at the Bretton Woods international conference that the fixed course regime was introduced. This regime was based on

gold parity. To determine the currency parity of any currency against the US dollar, its gold value was compared to the gold value of the dollar. A monetary system is a broader concept than a currency system. However, some elements of the monetary system can also be elements of the currency system. For example, national currency. The national currency of any country is the national currency of that country. Therefore, the national currency is an element for both the monetary system and the currency system. But there are elements of the monetary system that, in our opinion, are not considered elements for the currency system. The following can be distinguished as such elements:

- composition of money circulation;
- organization and regulation of money circulation;
- money supply and composition;
- principles of monetary system organization.

In turn, some elements of the currency system are not considered elements of the monetary system. One such element is the regime of the national currency market. For example, the foreign exchange market in the Republic of Uzbekistan consists of two parts, namely the Republic Currency Exchange and the over-the-counter market. In the foreign exchange market, the US dollar and the euro are the transaction currency, while the soum acts as the valuation currency. Also, determining the procedure for using international settlement forms, which are an element of the currency system, is not considered an element of the monetary system. This is due to the fact that international settlement forms are used to pay foreign currency payments to foreign partners and are not directly related to payments in national currency. According to the methodology of the International Monetary Fund, in order to determine the international currency liquidity of each country, gold-currency reserves are divided by the amount of one-year import of goods and the obtained result is multiplied by 100%. If this indicator is 50 percent and higher, then this country is considered liquid in international currency. The

movement of gold-currency reserves affects the money supply. But money cannot rise to the level of an element for the system. Because the movement of gold-currency reserves is directly related to the implementation of international payments. The use of foreign currencies in settlements between residents of the country is generally prohibited. For example, according to Article 18 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Currency Regulation", the use of foreign currencies as a means of payment in settlements between residents is prohibited.

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